
The Age of FinTech: Implications for Research, Policy and Practice

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FinTech is inducing changes in how financial services (FS) are perceived, developed, promoted, delivered and consumed. Future of FinTech, however, is rooted in deliberate integrated actions to improve framework conditions related to consumer trust, regulation and scalability. Building on limited scholarship, this paper identifies the building blocks for the future of FinTech and provides prescriptive areas of focus to guide research, policy and practice. In sum, the purpose of the paper is to serve as a catalyst and a call for an integrative approach in developing a common understanding and interpretation of FinTech as a socially-constructed phenomenon at the intersection of research and technology management.

Keywords: FinTech; research; technology management; policy; framework.

1. Introduction

Financial services (FS) industry is undergoing accelerated change in parallel to technological affordances of the industry transformation. *FinTech*, an umbrella term used to describe innovative technology-enabled FS business models is inducing paradigmatic shift in how financial service firms deliver pecuniary and non-pecuniary benefits to interacting parties (Schueffel, 2016; Zavolokina *et al.*, 2016). The US Financial Stability Board defines FinTech as

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“technologically enabled financial innovation that could result in new business models, applications, processes or products with an associated material effect on financial markets and institutions and the provision of financial services.” Driven by digitization and digitalization (for discussion on interpretations see, [Gobble, 2018](#)), the promise of FinTech is now a feature of global discussions ([Bofondi and Gobbi, 2017](#); [Carney, 2017](#)).

On the one hand, FinTech is forcing legacy financial institutions to clarify their strategies, develop new capabilities and transform their cultures ([Buchak et al., 2018](#); [Leong and Sung, 2018](#); [Nonninger and Tesfaye, 2018](#)). On the other hand, FinTech start-ups stand to benefit from technology-enabled capabilities, characterized by higher knowledge intensity and lower internal resource dependency ([Mention and Torkkeli, 2012](#); [Dapp, 2014](#); [Philippon, 2016](#)). There exists little doubt that FinTech is revolutionizing how FS are developed, promoted, delivered and consumed ([Dapp, 2014](#)). However, the jury is still out on the future of FinTech. The renewed momentum is delivering double-edged consequences — modernizing financial architecture and catalyzing behavioral change on one end and, disrupting incumbent employers, service models and regulations on the other end.

The research on this multifaceted socially constructed FinTech phenomenon is still in its infancy, but growing steadily (for recent reviews see, [Gomber et al., 2017](#); [Zavolokina et al., 2016](#)). [Zavolokina et al. \(2016\)](#) position the first debate on the concept and definition of FinTech. Drawing on use of FinTech term in popular media, they conceptualized FinTech as a digital innovation focused on creating, changing, improving and disrupting information technology applications in finance and create competition in the sector, achieved through new services, products, processes or business models. More recently, [Gomber et al. \(2017\)](#) in adopting the digital innovation in finance premise reviewed the current state of research in digital finance from a business innovation perspective. They revealed the digital finance cube and argued that future research direction on the topic rests at the intersection of business functions, technologies and technological concepts, and types of institutions involved in the FinTech. Collectively, these reviews showcase the peculiarities of how FinTech is conceived in academia and practice. Other sets of studies have explored the FinTech universe, for instance, its applications across domains of banking functions (e.g., [Gomber et al., 2018](#); [Schwab and Guibaud, 2016](#); [Stoekli et al., 2018](#)) and types of customer-centric and value-creating digitalization transformations brought about by FinTechs to retail banking (e.g., [Davies et al., 2016](#); [Dhar and Stein, 2017](#); [Gozman et al., 2018](#); [Marjanovic and Murthy, 2016](#); [Shim and Shin, 2016](#)).

However, to the best of our knowledge, there exists limited synthesis and insights on the building blocks of FinTech, conceptualizing aspects which may guide discussions on the future-oriented implications for FinTech research, policy and practice. This paper thus advances the argument that for an industry that is rapidly shaping the way we live; it seems necessary to identify its building blocks and guide future actions. Moving beyond the promise of FinTech, its definitions and domains of application, our belief (and hope) is that a coherent understanding of the future-oriented challenges and opportunities can shape deliberate actions today. In believing so, we acknowledge that FinTech is not confined to start-up ventures and is increasingly adopted by incumbents for its competitiveness and scalable applications (Alt and Puschmann, 2016; Schwab and Guibaud, 2016). Despite the variations in functional FinTech perspectives such as those related to compliance and regulatory issues i.e., “RegTech” (Gomber *et al.*, 2018), insurance business, i.e., InsurTech (Stoekli *et al.*, 2018), retail banking (Schwab and Guibaud, 2016), and similarly, the building blocks for the future of FinTech reflect common considerations for how finance technology can be made possible to serve societal needs and demands. Interactions among main subjects and topics related to FinTech in literature are indeed focused on challenges related to awareness and adoption (Schulte and Liu, 2018), regulatory and privacy concerns (Ducas and Wilner, 2017; Traynor *et al.*, 2017) and inhibitors of new products and services related to business models (Chen, 2016) and innovation collaboration or implementation (Au and Kauffman, 2008; Saksonova and Kuzmina-Merlino, 2017). Therefore, to synthesize a framework for future of FinTech, we set the following research questions which will guide the reader through the paper: (1) *what are the future-oriented challenges and opportunities of FinTech?* and (2) *what are the building blocks and implications for future research, policy and practice in the context of FinTech?*

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In the *FinTech: the end of a beginning*, current framework perspectives are identified, which will serve as the basis for future-oriented discussion. To do that, this paper provides a glimpse of the rapidly growing global FinTech phenomenon, leading to our practice-oriented framework building approach. Subsequently, in *future of FinTech: an introduction*, challenges and opportunities are outlined, situating the discussions on open innovation and interoperability of framework conditions for growth and scalability across borders. For illustrative purposes, the paper relies on the European Union’s (EU) FinTech conditions, in part due to the presence of rich regional and EU-wide policy, academic and

popular press publications. Our *concept map for the future of FinTech* reflects three components — building blocks for the future of FinTech, action lines and areas of potential impact. Thereafter, a summary is included in *conclusion, limitations and future directions*. Here, the paper identifies potential implications for research, policy and practice of FinTech and how the adopted approach builds on the existing promise of FinTech. Collectively, the aim of this paper is to inspire new ways to explore and explain the socially-constructed multifaceted FinTech phenomenon.

2. FinTech: The End of a Beginning

Technological affordances, coupled with the proliferation of open innovation business models (Brunswicker and Chesbrough, 2018) are promoting early internationalization and higher knowledge intensity (Autio *et al.*, 2000). For instance, the set of products that traditionally have been within the exclusive remit of licensed credit institutions — payment services and loans — are now the most prominent FS provided by non-traditional technology-enabled financial firms representing a wide array of customer-centric value propositions and business models (EBA, 2016). FinTech firms are developing new ways for accessing, delivering, experiencing and co-creating FS (personalized solutions and mass customization). Diversity through portability of digital financial products, hybrid and cross-industry business models in new markets are the underlying premise of FinTech with benefits promoted as greater transparency and improved risk management with instant evaluation of feedback and adjustment of service in real-time.

For policy making, the FinTech market is quickly becoming too large to ignore. Industry reports on FinTech investments (see, e.g., Accenture, 2016; Cortina and Schmukler, 2018; Demirguc-Kunt *et al.*, 2018; World Economic Forum, 2015) provide an appreciation for the state-of-the-art. About five years ago, an Accenture (2016) report noted that FinTech investments rose dramatically between 2013 and 2014, from US\$4.05 billion in 2013 to US\$12.2 billion in 2014. Although such reports on FinTech are limited in scope (i.e., often based on regional data) and uncoordinated, in 2015 there were at least 4,000 FinTech firms with more than a dozen identified as “unicorns” (valued over US\$1 billion) (The Economist, 2015). The global investment in FinTech was US\$22.3 billion in 2015, 12 times more than five years prior in 2010 (Accenture, 2016). Since then, KPMG (2018) reported that global investment in FinTech reached US\$24.7 billion across 1,076 deals in 2016. More recent CBIInsights (2018) reports identified the top 250

FinTech firms which collectively raised over US\$31.85 billion in 2018. KPMG's (2018) FinTech Pulse report stated that global FinTech investment increased from US\$50.8 billion in 2017 to US\$111.8 billion in 2018, more than double due to unprecedented number of deals through multiple channels.

Not surprisingly, the FinTech investment and growth trends are also attracting scholarly attention, evident from special academic journal issues like *Journal of Management Information Systems*' "Special Issue: Financial Information Systems and the FinTech Revolution" (Gomber *et al.*, 2018), *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Management's* "Innovation for Financial Services" (Mention *et al.*, 2012) and "Towards a Philosophy of Financial Technologies" in *Philosophy and Technology* (Coeckelbergh *et al.*, 2018). Amongst these, some scholars have argued that the concept of FinTech is not new, dating back nearly 150 years of technology-led shifts in perceptions, processes and practices related to FS (Arner *et al.*, 2016a). Alt and Puschmann (2016) categorized these technological shifts into five phases lasting 20 years each, both pre- and post-1960. Building on this typology, Puschmann (2017) categorized future directions for FinTech research across three dimensions: innovation degree (disruptive, incremental), innovation object (business model, product/service, organization, process, system) and innovation scope (inter- and intra-organizational). More recently, Gai *et al.* (2018) provided a framework with five FinTech dimensions — privacy and security, data techniques, hardware and infrastructure, applications and management and service models. Likewise, Gozman *et al.* (2018) in reviewing the FinTech startups that participated in SWIFT's Inn Tribe competition, proposed a conceptual framework for FinTech innovation. Their FinTech ecosystem model for competition and cooperation identified three constructs — services, business infrastructure and technical components to capture different FinTech innovation types. They referred to FinTech components as granular technologies adopted by both startups and incumbents (e.g., Big data, artificial intelligence) which form the building blocks of FinTech. A parallel stream of FinTech research has focused on the tensions between financial market stability and regulation (Arner *et al.*, 2017; Buchak *et al.*, 2018; Magnuson, 2018). Scholars in this stream have situated discussions on capabilities afforded by FinTech. The central message being that future of FinTech is rooted in directing digital capabilities to reduce compliance costs, manage risks and enhance trust in the financial system (Bofondi and Gobbi, 2017; Boot, 2017).

Some scholars, however, have focused on reaching a consensual definition of FinTech by drawing attention to categories of its applications. For instance,

Leong and Sung (2018) summarized FinTech across four applications (payments, advisory, financing, compliance) and defined FinTech as “a cross-disciplinary subject that combines finance, technology management and innovation management” (p. 75), a purview adopted for the purpose of this paper. Likewise, Zavolokina *et al.* (2016) reviewed how popular press perceives FinTech and summarized the definitions across three dimensions — input (combination of technology, organization and money flow), mechanism (create or improve change, disrupt, apply IT to finance, create competition) and output (new products, services or business models). The debate on what is FinTech is still ongoing (Leong and Sung, 2018).

The lack of this consensus has also shifted focus away from FinTech as a research object toward FinTech as a context. Studies at the periphery have discussed the use of FinTech as a tool for financial inclusion and poverty reduction (see, e.g., Jones, 2018). Others such as Lee and Kim (2015) focused on the application of FinTech (i.e., crowdfunding), while Arner *et al.* (2015) and Jagtiani and John (2018) focused on consumer protection and behavior to attract attention toward regulatory challenges. More recently, Gozman *et al.* (2018) analyzed 403 FinTech start-ups that participated in SWIFT’s Innotribe competition to create a foundational understanding of the global FinTech landscape. They clustered FinTech firms based on core markets, business infrastructures and underlying technologies. Their conclusion resonates with our premise that FinTech firms leverage diverse and varied range of innovation strategies for value creation through cooperative and competitive mechanisms, which calls for a foundational perspective for future research.

3. Future of FinTech: An Introduction

3.1. *Opportunity affordances for the future of FinTech*

The increased recognition of the role of FinTech in FS markets is bringing a “start-up-like” mentality to corporate organizations. Incumbent financial institutions are beginning to embrace the concept of “FinTech intrapreneurship”, an inward-looking approach to innovation, where teams and individuals are developing and driving new venture initiatives within large FS organization (Nicoletti, 2017). This approach allows for inbound and outbound knowledge and capabilities exchange, related and unrelated diversification strategies deployment and the creation on an open, collaborative and co-creative environment, conducive to FinTech and financial innovation (Martovoy *et al.*, 2015). Emerging open innovation practices within FS, thus, encourage and promote FinTech intrapreneurial activities that can

cut through corporate layers, sourcing lean, agile, experimentation strategies, along with bringing new vision, energy, direction and purpose to incumbent financial institutions (Bogusz *et al.*, 2018).

This new regime is expected to increase competition, co-opetition, customer centricity and cross-sectoral collaboration (account aggregation) in the banking industry. Access to customer banking data, conditional to customer consent, will enable FinTech firms and incumbent banks to provide tailored, innovative and wide-ranging payment products and services. Customers stand to benefit from competitive pricing through mobilization of secure Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), enabling easier comparison of banking choices. Based on open banking principles, access to banking data will also enable consumers to access innovative services to assist them to analyze their expenditure and better manage their finances. Thus, new regulatory regimes associated with open banking are shaping the future of FinTech by establishing banking-as-a-platform and marketplace banking.

3.2. Challenges for the future of FinTech

FinTech start-ups are faced with numerous challenges during early stages of their product/service development. FinTech start-ups are faced with difficulties in terms of portraying a hyper-clear value proposition of intangible/service-based FinTech offerings and understanding both users and product/service market fit (Altenhain and Heinemann, 2018). In principle, venture capitalists (VCs) and angel investors' valuations can make funding difficult in terms of leveraging lean business models and scalable platforms (Bömer and Schwienbacher, 2018; Cumming and Schwienbacher, 2018). Furthermore, VCs are looking for unique, new and differentiated offerings and demonstration of scalability and mitigation of risk.

FinTech start-ups experience hurdles in terms of securing operating leverage, especially due to significant upfront investment requirements for building intellectual property (Lee and Shin, 2018). Therefore, for FinTech start-ups acquiring early-stage funding, proof of concept development is an onerous barrier due to an inability to showcase a proven business model, find the right market and determine the customer/user demographics. As Still *et al.* (2019) identified FinTech start-ups need to develop competencies in relation to understanding innovation relationships. To gain competitive edge, FinTech firms need to leverage emerging technologies, awareness and realization of which calls for dynamic capabilities related to screening, auditing, roadmapping and forecasting. Yet for incumbents, key technological trends manifested in FinTech product/service offerings requires adopting efficient

technological methods against legacy systems, leading to barriers toward new technology integration (Moshirian *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, from the human side, FinTech start-ups are faced with talent shortage challenges. Against the backdrop of skills development, talent attraction and diversified agile teams realizing the human to digital customer interaction shift is a significant FinTech challenge (Dove, 2018; Mei *et al.*, 2018; Wang and Huang, 2018).

Finally, customer and institutional trust results in lower customer adoption. FinTech start-ups find it very hard to reach customers who are used to traditional FS (Claessens *et al.*, 2018). Above all, FinTech start-ups need to battle with misconceptions and concerns with regards to security and reliability of data inertia over innovation — a challenge that requires building relational and behavioral trust (Salampasis *et al.*, 2014). FinTech has brought to light foundational questions with regards to regulatory interventions calling for a new dialogue on the “if, when, what and how” aspects of regulation and compliance in the context of responsible (ethical) innovation (Magnuson, 2018). Disruptive forces coupled with evolved need for multi-disciplinary talent pose challenges for FinTech firms and regulators alike, in terms of gaining consumer trust, developing supportive regulatory infrastructure and enhancing FinTech’s ability to scale-up and deploy solutions across borders.

4. Concept Map for the Future of FinTech

A concept map is captured in Fig. 1. Concept maps are widely used in the literature and practice to express connections between knowledge domains and constructs (Cañas and Novak, 2008). A concept map generally includes a graphical representation of a set of concepts depicted in geometric shapes, where relationships are shown via connecting lines with linking words or phrases to specify the relationship. Thus, concept maps through graphical structure and content form the basis for the development of a conceptual framework (Daley, 2004).

In the rest of this section, the five building blocks and its implications for research, policy and practice of FinTech are discussed. Collectively, our aim is to guide coherent efforts to shape the future of FinTech. FinTech, as “a new financial industry that applies technology to improve financial activities” (Schueffel, 2016, p. 32) is built upon distributed business models of value creation and value capture from customer-centric innovations (Gozman *et al.*, 2018). Gozman *et al.* (2018) proposed that a key challenge of the future of FinTech is for policy makers to find a balance between protecting consumers and fostering innovations such that it draws upon existing regional

Fig. 1. Concept map for future of FinTech.

capabilities and leads to further business and employment opportunities. In the same vein, *Gozman et al. (2018)* posited that future implications for FinTech research and practice rest in understanding how large and start-up firms can come together for value-creating FinTech applications designed for diverse stakeholder groups, including characterizing forces that influence globalization, integrated standards of operation and cooperation amongst firms. Indeed, proliferation of FinTech innovations precipitates in the shifting paradigms of innovation adaptability within the wider FS industry and as such calls for a continuous adaptation and evaluation of aggregate value across stakeholder groups. Taking a broad perspective of FinTech innovations, the purpose of the concept map is to attract attention to increase the integration of the building blocks to transactions and transformations in the primary finance market (e.g., payment and cashflow solutions) alongside adaptations in the secondary markets (e.g., supply chain service models such

as straight through processing within sharing economy). The building blocks in this view relate to incumbents and start-ups alike and highlight the role of intermediaries in shaping the increasingly porous boundaries between traditional and new business model systems. While incumbents need to generate and implement scalable innovations to remain relevant through their satellite start-ups and FinTech innovation labs; the FinTech start-ups also need to maintain progress toward scalable and integrated solutions. The holistic purview thus calls for an interconnected view of the building blocks for the future of FinTech.

4.1. *Collaboration*

Collaboration is a critical building block for the future of FinTech, particularly since most FinTech start-ups are likely to fail if they do not build partnerships (Capgemini, 2018). It is thus not surprising that FinTech businesses are seeking out opportunities to network with specialized external partners to leverage on resources and generate profits from otherwise increasingly lower margins (Davies *et al.*, 2016; Shim and Shin, 2016; Gimpel *et al.*, 2018). There is a need to coordinate research, policy and practice on regulation in FS at a global level to enable FinTech to grow, scale-up and internationalize (Gozman *et al.*, 2018). While not every FinTech start-up has the potential to scale, those performing with excellence in their core businesses may benefit from strategic collaboration within and across international borders to address traditional incumbent customers' pain points for scale and distribution (Verhage, 2018). Collaboration between various stakeholder groups (e.g., incumbents, central banks, regulators, start-ups, consumers and ancillary supply chain providers) plays a formative role in facilitating value-creating and market-enhancing innovations. Given the applied and often disruptive nature of FinTech, implications of FinTech solutions can only be realized if researchers, policy makers and practitioners have access to suitable trend and technology assessment tools which facilitate transparent and real-time information processing of large amounts of diverse sets of data. Besides, FinTech research so far has adopted a narrow domain and problem-based approach to target isolated diffusion challenges or application opportunities afforded by technological advances (Gomber *et al.*, 2018; Milian *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, dissimilar FinTech appraisal and evaluation methods and differences in market contexts have further limited the value of current FinTech research toward policy making and multi-market growth strategies in practice. Consumer viewpoints in FinTech research have

also been fragmented and often focused on functional technology-push perspectives found in practice (see, [Arwas and Soleil, 2016](#); [Derks et al., 2018](#)). [Pousttchi and Dehnert \(2018\)](#), for instance, focused on the impact of digitalization on retail banking, attracting attention to how technologies are shaping consumer behavior toward search, purchase and use of FS. Yet, a systematic, cohesive and joint research agenda informed by stakeholder's views and roles in conceptualizing, developing and delivering technologies has the potential to shape future awareness, regulation and growth of FinTech firms through deeper understanding of design, manipulation and impact of market exchanges ([Ellig and Fike, 2016](#); [Gomber et al., 2018](#)).

One plausible exploratory method at this formative stage would be to conduct in-depth interviews with key stakeholders and market players to delineate perceptions, processes and practices in the context of FinTech. The key stakeholders and market players related to FinTech may come from various subsegments, from FS institutions, industry associations, representations such as the banking federations, regulators and supervisors, policy making organizations, and entrepreneurship and venturing catalysts (such as accelerators, incubators, landing pads, and regulatory sandboxes). A coherent discussion in such studies should aim to (a) discuss evolution of FinTech trends, challenges as well as current products and services, (b) analyze the changes in supply and value chains, with a focus on intermediation-disintermediation-re-intermediation and (c) assess impact of national regulatory processes on FinTech investment and innovation performance.

4.2. *Awareness and expertise*

The FinTech landscape now includes not only start-ups but also incumbents who are able to leverage distinctive innovation capabilities ([Davies et al., 2016](#)). Thus, coupled with up-skilling of FinTech, research and policy efforts are needed toward development of compliance toolkits, enabling diverse types of FinTech firms and/or initiatives to meet regulatory requirements (for a typology of FinTech firms and initiatives see, [Eickhoff et al., 2017](#); [Milian et al., 2019](#)). Moreover, for regulators, awareness is essential for rapidly emerging technologies and the consequences they bring to market integrity, stability and sustainability ([Buchak et al., 2018](#); [Magnuson, 2018](#)). FinTech start-ups are generally more “in touch” with the public and thus cross-sectoral knowledge sharing between regulators and FinTech to enhance awareness of consumer habits and behavior can contribute positively toward building consumer trust and loyalty for digital platforms ([Arner et al., 2016b](#)). While tools and

practices have been developed to envisage likely evolutions of trends, FinTech researchers need to leverage the synergies between strategic planning and strategic design processes in creation of future value.

The design for behavior change which draws from research in psychology and other disciplines is one approach that can inform decision and strategies for a desired FinTech future (see, e.g., Fogg, 2003; Lockton *et al.*, 2010). Evidence also suggests that firms that apply foresight are indeed those which achieve a sustainable competitive advantage (Grant, 2010). Figuratively speaking, in foresight, the focus is directed on "... the world as it could be, through the imagination and realization of possible futures..." (Grand and Wiedmer, 2010, p. 2). Specifically, strategic design-foresight methods in the emerging field of FinTech can generate a range of possible future and strategic options, providing an enhanced understanding of possible challenges and strategic risks and best practices for alternative futures (Heger and Rohrbeck, 2012). Collectively, application of these methods in a practice-oriented research design can serve as behavioral intervention for building capacity toward future thinking and cognitive adaptability (Vecchiato and Roveda, 2010). Analysis, interpretation and protection of practices for responsible FinTech innovation are a part of the foresight process that can inform strategic thinking and strategy formulation. In a further step, foresight exercise can help policy makers investigate upcoming technologies and their potential usage for FinTech entrepreneurship (Wonglimpiyarat, 2017; see also Ernst and Young, 2015).

In this sense, future of FinTech is rooted in behavioral intervention methodologies that foster regulatory compliance and enable FinTech scale-up based on creative interpretations derived from Socio-cultural, Technological, Economic, and Political (STEP) drivers of change (Nicoletti, 2017). Specifically, employing a design-inspired foresight research approach, can help gaining deeper insights through Delphi-like techniques, thus, moving away from the traditional management practices of predicting the future based on current knowledge. The Delphi technique is among the more established foresight methods, first introduced by the RAND Corporation in the 1950s (Linstone and Turoff, 1975). Adopted for practice-oriented research, it can allow groups of regulators, supervisors, advisors, entrepreneurs and experts to consider and reflect upon interpretations of opportunities, obstacles and risks related to FinTech from early stage design and piloting to internationalization. A further strength of the Delphi method is that it allows experts to be geographically dispersed, which

means that participants can interact around the FinTech topic and receive sequential feedback without the need for constant physical proximity (Lee and Shin, 2018).

4.3. *Market economy and sustainability*

FinTech venture challenges discussed above include those arising from multiple and cross-country regulatory authorities/jurisdictions. Under open and collaborative environment, trust plays a central role in efforts toward harmonizing compliance frameworks for human-centric financial innovations (Salampasis *et al.*, 2014). Friction between incumbents and early-stage startups needs development of relational and behavioral trust, bifurcating misconceptions and concerns for cyber security and reliability of data inertia over innovation (Stewart and Jürjens, 2018). From a regional policy perspective, regulatory measures related to equity requirements, “safe” experimentation of new technologies and less cumbersome supervisory arrangements are needed alongside tighter rules and higher supervision at an international level (Arner *et al.*, 2017; Baxter, 2016). These are particularly important as FinTech solutions continue to shift financial infrastructure away from traditional centralized networks toward digitalized operations through networked domain-specific ecosystemic partners, and even incorporate decentralized solutions (e.g., use of blockchain technology) (Alt and Puschmann, 2016; Pousttchi and Dehnert, 2018).

Sustainable development of the FinTech thus calls for a focus on responsible innovations considering the tenets of embedded trust — demographic diversity, knowledge sharing attitude, ambidextrous thinking, collaborative culture, customer adoption of FinTech innovations and efficient use of resources (e.g., lower acquisition and operational costs) (Salampasis *et al.*, 2014; Haddad and Hornuf, 2016). Du *et al.* (2018) through a study on blockchain identify supportive culture as an important element of FinTech actualization. Gold and Kursh (2017) concentrated on robo-advisors and how this technology is perceived and responded to by decision-makers in traditional asset management firms. The expansive review of FinTech literature by Milian *et al.* (2019) highlighted the gap (and hence the need) for research at the intersection of financial technologies and its adoption, with reference to building capabilities in dealing with externalities such as legal and compliance issues. Accordingly, behavioral research aimed at building regulatory capabilities for FinTech entrepreneurs through specialized knowledge transfer training programs can nurture an emerging FinTech entrepreneurship landscape.

4.4. *Internationalization*

As it stands, 95% of FinTech firms fail when they reach the scale-up phase (Pai, 2017). The primary reason is that FinTech often fail to integrate and deploy solutions beyond regional and national regulatory boundaries and fail to target customers at infection points (Strange and Rampell, 2016). Yet, examples abound of FinTech firms that have experienced accelerated growth, with studies pointing to China as one of the main centers for digital finance innovations (see, Milian *et al.*, 2019; Stern *et al.*, 2017). For instance, Yu'E Bao, a Chinese internet money market fund owned by Ant Financial (an affiliate of Alibaba) took advantage of the opportunity to generate business from excess cash transactions from digital wallet transactions and went from no assets to US\$90 billion in 10 months. However, Yu'E Bao became “too big to fail” in under a year. For Arner *et al.* (2016a), the FinTech challenge is rooted in managing the tension between futuristic FinTech innovation frameworks and trust in the market. A broad range of challenges exist in cross-border regulation of FinTech, including those related to commerce of services, operational controls for regulatory risk and money laundering, privacy and security of consumers and assets, structural validation of data storage and disclosure, and collaboration on nationally sensitive and non-sensitive information, amongst others (Arner *et al.*, 2017; Kopp *et al.*, 2017). Regulators in such cases face the issue of knowing *if* they should regulate, *what* to regulate, *when* to regulate and *how* to regulate in a rapidly emerging FinTech space (Arner *et al.*, 2017; Gomber *et al.*, 2018). Implications for research include a need to build repository of FinTech best practices, regulations and experimentations frameworks, aimed at mapping existing worldwide intelligence. These maps could then be funneled into customized tools and processes for enabling and improving internationalization initiatives. A behavioral research approach could be aimed at the cognition-context spectrum (Clark, 2010), taking an agentic lens to examine the impact of “think local” and “think global” mindsets and encourage responsible choices and actions (Niedderer, 2007, 2014).

4.5. *Business model innovation*

Untangling tension between regulatory requirements and acceptance of consumer-focused innovations in an otherwise conservative regulatory bias for new and emerging technologies calls for a focus on business model innovation. FinTech firms have a need to test, configure and design several applications integrating different and usually heterogeneous technologies.

Testing through live simulations and realistic operating conditions is a vital part within the development process, especially within a lean/agile venturing environment (Arner *et al.*, 2016a). An experimentation test-bed is a platform (usually cloud-based) grounded in the exploration–exploitation conundrum, allowing users to create their own experiments for rigorous and replicable testing over the web using state-of-the-art technologies at a rapid pace. As a tool that has already gained a lot of traction and attention (Balan *et al.*, 2014), allows users to acquire experimental validation within a laboratory-based, open, dynamic, stable and secure environment. This validation allows for faster deployment of early prototypes in the real world. In principle, the key objectives of a FinTech experimentation testbed are (a) technical analysis and assessment of a FinTech solution under real conditions, (b) evaluation of customer adoption of a FinTech solution, (c) magnitude of service usability, potential, efficiency and effectiveness with users in the development process and (d) testing of technical stability (see, e.g., Patel *et al.*, 2017). In this context, a FinTech experimentation testbed aims at removing barriers to entry for FinTech innovators and entrepreneurs by providing a degree of experimentation realism (Sanchez *et al.*, 2014) and driving FinTech innovative technological advancement and breakthroughs.

Like-wise “test-and-learn” or “regulatory sandbox”, is a dynamic and flexible regulatory framework, aimed at providing a temporary, safe — and under specific pre-determined conditions — relaxation of certain flexible and lenient regulatory requirements and obligations (Dostov *et al.*, 2017; Thomadakis, 2017). This safe environment allows early-stage start-ups to conduct real-world market reach and market reaction testing on their products/services, fine-tune their business models, and design the unique value proposition of their offerings without the obligation to obtain a full license and clear regulatory hurdles, reducing the barriers to entry and regulatory costs.

Regulatory sandboxes serve as a “diagnostic tool” to help FinTech entrepreneurs determine their innovation capacity, validate their technological concept and end-customer market adoption, while planning strategically toward scale, growth and impact. Moreover, regulatory sandboxes help early-stage FinTech ventures build long-term experimentation capabilities (cyclical process of testing — validated learning — pivoting) that are essential to FinTech innovation, allowing for validated learning through brief looped iterations with customers/users. They provide the opportunity for customer feedback and development of mutual value propositions, on the premise of minimizing potential systemic risk and protecting consumer interest (Tsai and Peng, 2017). It is believed that regulatory sandboxes have

the potential to provide a harmonized strategy for governing financial innovation (Iris, 2017) within a “smart regulation” paradigm shift (Zetzsche *et al.*, 2017). The underlying reasoning behind regulatory sandboxes is to provide foundations for sound competition within the financial industry (Noh, 2017). Despite lack of harmonized framework conditions (see, Sajtos and Törös, 2018), regulatory sandboxes can foster cooperative forces between incumbent financial institutions and FinTech firms by limiting wasteful efforts and expenditure on resources for understanding and safely testing technological innovations (Arner *et al.*, 2015). However, their net positive or negative impact to FinTech scalability and growth is yet to be empirically and systematically examined (Bromberg *et al.*, 2017). Accordingly, from a research implication purview, it is important to explore and explain how exactly regulatory sandboxes helps in creating a cross-sectoral, start-up friendly, use-case tailored global reach ecosystem.

5. Conclusion, Limitations and Future Directions

This paper addresses the following questions: (1) *what are the future-oriented challenges and opportunities of FinTech?* and (2) *what are the building blocks and implications for future research, policy and practice in the context of FinTech?* Discussions are situated on the current framework conditions and limited scholarship on the topic to identify the five building blocks for the future of FinTech. This section provides some reflection on these discussions to identify its limitations and future directions for research in the field.

The rapidly growing importance of FinTech on a global scale is firstly acknowledged. FinTech, as an industry, is now “too big to fail”, a perspective that departs from the “too small to care” and “too big to ignore” continuum. In other words, without appropriate regulatory attention, the future of FinTech may be bleak, with gaps in market risk management filled by third-party speculators and analysts which may not benefit the end consumers (see, Mugerman *et al.*, 2019). The disruptive forces and their implications for FinTech, regulators and wider financial markets were then discussed, leading to the identification of limited literature on FinTech frameworks and the observation that studies found no coherent understanding of FinTech and its implications (e.g., Arner *et al.*, 2015; Gomber *et al.*, 2017; Zavolokina *et al.*, 2016). This ignited the interest for this paper and shaped its objective of unveiling a formative concept map. It is hoped that, collectively, these efforts will serve as the basis to understand perceptions, processes and practices of socially-constructed phenomenon of FinTech from a multi-faceted

perspective. Moreover, this paper draws on the future-oriented challenges and opportunities related to FinTech growth and scalability across borders. This brings value to those researchers who are searching for the problem in practice to advance research on FinTech. This paper also presents a problem-driven framework building approach which may be used to explore new and emerging fields related to innovation and technology management. The adopted approach is particularly beneficial when the objective is to build a practice-oriented framework for a phenomenon from limited scholarship. Overall, this paper contributes to the wider research on technology management, digital finance, and digital innovation by drawing attention to the cross-sector implications of rapidly growing and pervasive FinTech market.

This study has several limitations which are noteworthy to understand opportunities for future research. First, its approach is based on nuances found in practice, policy actions and widely dispersed literature on FinTech. A systematic review of literature is not suitable at this stage since the field is still in its infancy, however such an approach could be beneficial to establish clear research propositions in the future. The aim of this paper was not to evaluate current methodologies and actions applied to shape the future of FinTech. This approach was purposefully adopted as nearly all the large-scale efforts (e.g., the EU H2020 actions identified above) have been made in the last four years and their impact is yet to be realized. In the future, a benchmarking or time series analysis method coupled with trend extrapolation and impact analysis could inform how investments in FinTech actions plans are benefiting consumers, FinTech entrepreneurs and financial markets. A notable feature of the references we relied on is that they are regionalized with no clear framework for comparative analysis. In this view, the proposed concept map for the future of FinTech provides the building blocks for analyses across regional and international borders and has limited value in understanding the specific role and responsibilities of various stakeholders in shaping the future of FinTech. Future studies could complement this concept map through empirical work that delves deeper as data build around globalized FinTech markets. Perhaps, the recent work by *Milian et al. (2019)* which explored how FinTech literature has evolved over time can complement this work and help researchers and policy makers in developing novel research designs and understanding domain agnostic building blocks for the future of FinTech, respectively.

In considering the economic, governance and behavioral topics related to FinTech, it is noted that opportunities abound for technology and innovation scholars to take the position as lead contributors to the future of FinTech, at

the intersection of regulatory frameworks, emerging financial technologies and the entrepreneurial environments. Researchers should accordingly be encouraged to adopt multi-disciplinary approaches to extend the concept map and bring meaningful results to shape regulatory forces, technological innovations and behavioral strategies of FinTech.

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